

Heal Talk

Endo

Talk

Vital Pulp Therapy

Dr. Rajiv K. Chugh
BDS, MDS

Secretary General, International College of Dentists
Section-6 (India, Sri Lanka & Nepal Section)
Member, Dental Council of India
1st Vice- President, Indian Dental Association, H.O.

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The human dental pulp is a type of connective tissue found within the hard tissues (dentine and enamel) of the teeth. The vitality of dental pulp is essential for long-term tooth survival. The dental pulp is at risk of infection when exposed to damage such as caries or tooth fracture, which can lead to pain, necrosis, and infection of the jaw bone and the surrounding tissues. The aim of vital pulp therapy is to maintain the healthy pulp tissue and stimulate the formation of reparative dentine by eliminating bacteria from the dentin-pulp complex. The basis of carrying out the Vital Pulp Therapy is the ability of the pulp to repair in the absence of microbial contamination. There are several different treatment options for vital pulp therapy in extensively decayed or traumatized teeth.

INTRODUCTION

Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is defined as a treatment which aims to preserve and maintain the pulp tissue that has been compromised but not destroyed by caries, trauma, or restorative procedures in a healthy state. Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is a potential alternative to root canal treatment. VPT is a restorative dental procedure that aims to treat teeth with compromised dental pulp without the full removal or excavation of all healthy pulp tissue. It is particularly important in the young adult tooth with incomplete apical root development. It has been recommended that VPT should be performed only in young patients because of the high healing capacity of pulp tissue compared to older patients. We all know that the vital pulp should be preserved if possible. The survival rate of vital teeth is known to be better than the endodontically treated teeth. Success of VPT is dependent on a variety of factors, including the amount of infected tissue, an adequate blood supply to the tooth, healthy periodontium, and the opportunity to create an appropriate coronal seal. One of the most important issues in VPT is the status of the pulp tissue. The traditional school of thought is that VPT should only be carried out in teeth with signs and symptoms of reversible pulpitis. Though the clinical signs and symptoms such as sensibility and pain testing do not precisely reflect the pulp condition. The degree of pulpal bleeding may be a better indicator of pulpal inflammatory status. Increased bleeding on exposure site that is difficult to stop, suggests that the inflammatory response extends deeper into the pulp tissue and the treatment procedure should be modified, like opting

from direct pulp cap to partial pulpotomy.

Factors affecting the success of Vital Pulp Therapy

1. The presence of an adequate blood supply is required for the maintenance of the pulp vitality.
2. The presence of a healthy periodontium is necessary for success of VPT, and teeth with moderate to severe periodontal disease are not suitable candidates for the treatment.
3. While selecting the cases for VPT- include teeth in which an appropriate coronal seal can be provided. The prognosis of VPT is significantly reduced in cases with inadequate coronal seal and subsequent bacterial microleakage.
4. Control of hemorrhage is necessary for the success of VPT. The pulp hemostasis can be achieved by applying mechanical pressure using a sterile cotton pellet which may be soaked in sterile water or saline. Sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) has also been successfully used as an agent in VPT that can control hemorrhage.
5. The choice of a suitable dressing material is another important factor in the success of VPT. Pulp covering material should be biocompatible, noncytotoxic, and antibacterial.

Let us review the commonly used VPT techniques, namely pulp capping and pulpotomy, in permanent teeth.

Indirect Pulp Capping

Indirect pulp capping is defined as a procedure in which carious dentin closest to the pulp, is preserved to avoid pulp exposure and is covered with a biocompatible material. Recent studies have shown a high survival rate (more than 90%) for permanent teeth after performing indirect pulp capping, without adverse clinical symptoms or pathologic signs on radiographs which were comparable to those of pulpectomy treatment. The intention of this treatment method is to protect the primary odontoblasts and promote reactionary dentin formation at the pulp-dentine junction. However, some primary odontoblasts may be destroyed depending on the severity of carious involvement of the dentin-pulp complex and reparative dentin is formed in conjunction with reactionary dentin. An important function of

the bioactive lining material is to stimulate the odontoblasts to form the reactionary and reparative dentin and promote remineralization of existing dentine, thus encouraging the dentin-pulp complex. Calcium hydroxide has been the material of choice for many years for indirect pulp capping because of its alkaline pH and biocompatible properties that induces pulpo-dentin remineralization. However, there have been concerns regarding its long-term solubility and lack of adhesion to dentin, some adhesive materials such as resin modified glass ionomer cements have been also suggested.

Materials

The pulp response to Calcium Hydroxide and Resin Modified Glass Ionomer Cement in deep cavities, has been found to be not significantly different between the two materials. Some materials such as antimicrobials and polycarboxylate cement combined with tannin-fluoride preparation are suitable as liner, since all these materials can reduce cariogenic bacteria and promote remineralization, as effectively as Calcium Hydroxide. Among the newer generation of materials mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) and Biodentine has been used as a lining material and was compared with Calcium Hydroxide. After 6 months, the success rate and the average thickness of newly formed dentin have been found to be similar. Biodentine and MTA are rich in calcium compounds and an increase in calcium ion concentration is known to aid hard-tissue formation. At all time periods, the amount of calcium ions released as well as the depth of incorporation into human root canal dentine were significantly higher in Biodentine than those found for MTA.

Procedure

There are two options in performing Indirect Pulp Capping treatment:

- (a) Incomplete caries removal with no re-entry.
- (b) Stepwise or two-step excavation approach. In stepwise caries treatment, carious dentin in proximity to the pulp remains at the first step and in a second visit some month later, a re-entry procedure is performed. In this step there is a complete removal of all carious tissue and a definitive restoration are provided. In step-wise approach, removal of carious dentin during re-entry, must be carried out with caution to avoid pulp exposure, since the remaining carious dentin may have become harder, but the thickness of the remaining dentin may be unchanged.

On reviewing the literature, it was found that the incomplete caries removal reduces the risk of pulpal exposure and postoperative pulpal symptoms compared with step wise caries removal. However, the amount of dentin that can be left in the cavity was not sufficiently clear. The consensus on this issue is to remove peripheral caries dentin completely to achieve firm marginal adhesion, to remove as much of the caries adjacent to the pulp as possible, and avoid pulp exposure.

Direct Pulp Capping

As per the American Association of Endodontists guideline, 2003- Direct pulp capping is defined as the treatment of a mechanical or traumatic vital pulp exposure by sealing the pulpal wound with a biomaterial placed directly on exposed pulp to facilitate formation of reparative dentin and maintenance of the vital pulp. It has been found that primary odontoblasts are destroyed at the site of pulpal exposure and inflammation is initiated, recruitment and differentiation of progenitor/stem cells in the underlying uninfected vital pulp is required to produce reparative dentin. Growth factors such as transforming growth factor (TGF) family released from the dentin matrix and extracellular matrix molecules can induce the differentiation of progenitor/stem cells into odontoblast-like cells. Pulp capping materials such as Calcium Hydroxide, Biodentine and MTA induce reparative dentin formation by causing the release of growth factors from the dentin matrix.

It has been recommended that Direct Pulp Capping should be performed only in teeth with a recent mechanical or traumatic pulp exposure. It seems that microorganisms are the key factor in outcome of Direct Pulp Capping. Undesirable results can be attributed to the infection due to either remaining bacteria, or new bacteria penetrating from filling margins. Thus, beside the use of rubber dam and aseptic treatment condition the cavity should be restored immediately with a bacteria-tight restoration.

Some researchers have evaluated the effect of age, sex, teeth, presence of spontaneous pain, size of exposure and bleeding on the success rate of treatment. However no significant influence has been found on the success rate except that less bleeding increases the healing of pulp tissues.

(The article is a review of literature. To be continued in the next issue.)